

DETERMINATION OF EARTHQUAKE KNOWLEDGE AND EARTHQUAKE AWARENESS LEVELS OF VOCATIONAL COLLEGE STUDENTS

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Abstract: Coping behaviors of individuals before, during and after an earthquake they may encounter; It is related to earthquake knowledge, consciousness, awareness and preparedness levels. The aim of this study is to determine the knowledge and awareness levels of vocational college students about earthquakes. The research was conducted at Trakya University Keşan Vocational College. The research group consisted of 126 students at five different programs of the vocational college. In the research, a survey form consisting of 35 questions was applied to students at Electricity, Automotive Technology, Tourism and Hotel Management, Laboratory and Veterinary Health and Child Development Programs. The obtained data were statistically evaluated. In the study, it was concluded that while the students' knowledge levels about earthquakes were high, their awareness levels were low. The vocational college students are required to receive effective earthquake awareness training.

Keywords: Earthquake, Knowledge, Awareness, Vocational College, Student.

I. INTRODUCTION

An earthquake is when the vibrations that occur when the energy accumulated deep in the earth's crust is suddenly released, spread as waves, reach the earth and shake the earth's surface [1]. Due to its geological, topographic and meteorological characteristics, our country is most frequently faced with earthquakes among natural disasters. Approximately 500.000 large and small earthquakes occur annually in the world, and an average of 23.000 in our country. As a result of nearly three hundred earthquakes in Turkey between 1900 and 2009, 100.000 people lost their lives, nearly 180.000 people were injured, and 600.000 houses were destroyed or became unusable. The economic losses caused by earthquakes in our country are estimated to be billions of dollars [2]. For this reason, every individual living in our country should have the right attitudes about how to cope with earthquakes.

Although the occurrence of an earthquake cannot be prevented, its possible damages can be minimized thanks to knowledge and technology. Being aware that we live in an earthquake country, we need to take the necessary precautions personally and socially. The characteristics of earthquakes and earthquake-causing faults that affect and/or may affect our country should be recognized. Awareness should be raised to create safe living spaces in society. Therefore, earthquake awareness training should be provided at all levels [3]. Therefore, the aim of our study is; To determine the knowledge and awareness levels of students studying at vocational college about earthquakes. It is thought that determining the earthquake knowledge and awareness levels of technician candidates at five different programs of the vocational college with this study and supporting this study with new studies on the society's earthquake knowledge, awareness, awareness, attitude towards earthquakes and preparedness against earthquakes will contribute to disaster risk management.

II. METHOD

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This research was conducted between April and May 2025 to determine the knowledge and awareness levels of Trakya University Keşan Vocational College students about earthquakes. The research group consists of 126 students at the Electricity, Automotive Technology, Tourism and Hotel Management, Laboratory and Veterinary Health and Child Development Programs of the vocational college. The survey form applied as a data collection form in the research was prepared using the data obtained from the literature review [4-6]. The students participating in the research were asked 5 questions to obtain their demographic information. In the survey form, 10 questions were asked to the students to determine their earthquake knowledge levels, and 20 questions were asked to reveal their earthquake awareness levels, with Yes and No options. The data obtained was statistically evaluated.

III. FINDINGS

A. Demographic Findings

Within the scope of the study, among the students who answered the survey applied to five different Programs at Trakya University Keşan Vocational College, there were 45.24% (n:57) women and 54.76% (n:69) men. Since the survey was conducted with university students, it was seen that 98.41% (n:124) of the students were young individuals between the ages of 18-25. 28.57% (n:36) of the students were at Electricity, 15.87% (n:20) of the students were at Automotive Technology, 6.35% (n:8) of the students at Tourism and Hotel Management, 19.84% (n:25) of the students were Laboratory and Veterinary Health and 29.37% (n:37) of the students were Child Development Programs. The research group consisted of 99.21% (n:125) first-year students at Electricity, Automotive Technology, Tourism and Hotel Management, Laboratory and Veterinary Health and Child Development Programs and 0.79% (n:1) second-year students at Automotive Technology Program. 61.11% (n:77) of the students resided in state dormitory. Demographic characteristics of vocational college students were presented in Table 1.

Table: I Demographic Characteristics of the Vocational College Students (n:126)

Demographic Characteristics	n	%
Gender		
Female	57	45.24
Male	69	54.76
Age group		
18-21	117	92.86
22-25	7	5.55
26-	2	1.59
Department		
Electricity	36	28.57
Automotive Technology	20	15.87
Tourism and Hotel Management	8	6.35
Laboratory and Veterinary Health	25	19.84
Child Development	37	29.37
Grade Level		
1	125	99.21
2	1	0.79
Place of Residence at the University		
With his/her family	21	16.67
Student house	15	11.90
State dormitory	77	61.11
Private dormitory	13	10.32
Total	126	100.0

B. Findings Related to Earthquake Awareness

The distribution of earthquake awareness levels of the vocational college students was presented in Table 2.

Table: II Distribution of Earthquake Awareness Levels of the Vocational College Students (n:126)

Q No	QUESTIONS	YES (n)	YES (%)	NO (n)	NO (%)
6	Have you ever experienced a devastating earthquake?	24	19.05	102	80.95
7	Do you have information about the earthquake risk of the city you live in?	105	83.33	21	16.67
8	Do you think you are individually prepared for an earthquake?	51	40.48	75	59.52
9	Do you have an earthquake kit ready in your living space?	29	23.02	97	76.98
10	Are furniture that could tip over in your living space secured?	39	30.95	87	69.05
11	Do you think being aware of earthquakes can save lives?	119	94.44	7	5.56
12	Do you know your alternative shelter after the earthquake?	53	42.06	73	57.94
13	Have you received any training regarding earthquakes?	65	51.59	61	48.41
14	Does your university education inform you about the earthquake (before, during and after)?	55	43.65	71	56.35
15	Do you have information about the teams that should go to the scene after the earthquake?	95	75.40	31	24.60
16	Do you have information about the earthquake risk status of your school/house/dormitory?	82	65.08	44	34.92
17	Do you know safe areas at school/home/dorm?	79	62.70	47	37.30
18	Have you received first aid training?	46	36.51	80	63.49
19	Do you have earthquake-related applications on your phone?	50	39.68	76	60.32
20	Do you know how to evacuate the school/house/dormitory during an earthquake?	99	78.57	27	21.43
21	Do you trust the earthquake resistance of your school/house/dormitory?	36	28.57	90	71.43
22	Do you think the emergency exit directions at school/home/dormitory are sufficient?	52	41.27	74	58.73
23	Have you participated in an earthquake drill?	105	83.33	21	16.67
24	Do you think that local governments take the necessary precautions against a possible earthquake?	25	19.84	101	80.16
25	Do you have information about earthquake gathering areas?	115	91.27	11	8.73

C. Findings Related to Earthquake Knowledge

The distribution of earthquake knowledge levels of the vocational college students was presented in Table 3.

Table: III Distribution of Earthquake Knowledge Levels of the Vocational College Students (n:126)

Q No	QUESTIONS	YES (n)	YES (%)	NO (n)	NO (%)
26	During an earthquake, would you try to leave the building using the elevator?	9	7.14	117	92.86
27	During an earthquake, do you run to the stairs and try to throw yourself out of the building?	32	25.40	94	74.60
28	During an earthquake, do you wait for the shaking to pass without doing anything?	75	59.52	51	40.48
29	If you are on the ground or first floor during an earthquake, do you jump out of the window?	45	35.71	81	64.29
30	If you are in a high-rise building during an earthquake, do you climb to the upper floors?	19	15.08	107	84.92
31	Do you stand or sit at the doorstep during an earthquake?	92	73.02	34	26.98

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32	If you think you can go out within 5-10 seconds during an earthquake, would you do it quickly?	96	76.19	30	23.81
33	During an earthquake, do you lie down next to solid items such as a bed or sofa, protecting your head?	78	61.90	48	38.10
34	If you are in the kitchen during an earthquake, do you lie in the fetal position with your back against items such as the refrigerator or dishwasher?	74	58.73	52	41.27
35	If you are at school during an earthquake, do you know how to do the Drop-Cover-Hold movement next to or between desks?	115	91.27	11	8.73

As of the 26th question, 10 questions were asked the students to determine their knowledge levels about earthquakes. When the answers of the students given to the questions are evaluated, in terms of the average number of correct answers, it was seen that answered correctly 6.72 questions the students at Electricity Program, 7.55 questions the students at Automotive Technology Program, 5.75 questions the students at Tourism and Hotel Management Program, 6.96 questions the students at Laboratory and Veterinary Health Program and 7.46 questions the students at Child Development Program. The number of correct and incorrect answers given to the knowledge questions were presented in Figure 1. The number of correct and incorrect answers for the Electricity, Automotive Technology, Tourism and Hotel Management, Laboratory and Veterinary Health and Child Development Programs were presented in Figure 2.

Figure: 1 Number of Correct and Incorrect Answers to Knowledge Questions

Figure: 2 Number of Correct and Incorrect Answers for Programs of Vocational College

IV. DISCUSSION

In the study, it was determined that 80.95% (n:102) of the students had never experienced a devastating earthquake before. In the study which the earthquake knowledge and earthquake awareness levels of Trakya University Keşan Hakkı Yörük School of Health students were investigated; It was determined that 71.86 (n:143) of the students had never experienced a devastating earthquake before (7)[7]. In the study which the basic disaster awareness and preparedness levels of Gümüşhane University Kelkit Aydın Doğan Vocational School students were evaluated; It was published that 81.2% (n:229) of students who did not experience any disaster(8)[8]. In the study which the disaster awareness and disaster preparedness levels of Burdur Mehmet Akif Ersoy University Faculty of Economics and Administrative Sciences students were evaluated; It was reported that 61.7% (n: 213) of students who have not experienced any disaster to date (6)[6]. The research findings support the findings in the literature.

It was observed that 83.33% (n:105) of the students participating in the study had information about whether the city they lived in was at risk of earthquake or not. In the study which the earthquake knowledge and earthquake awareness levels of Trakya University Keşan Hakkı Yörük School of Health students were investigated; It was determined that 82.41% (n:164) of the students had information about the earthquake risk situation of the city they live in [7]. In a study conducted to determine the earthquake awareness of students of the Vocational School of Health Services at a state university; It was reported that 63.4% (n:225) of the students had knowledge about the earthquake risk situation of the city they lived in during their student years [5]. The research findings support the findings in the literature.

In the study, it was found that 59.52% (n:75) of the students individually thought that they were not prepared for the earthquake. In the study which the earthquake knowledge and earthquake awareness levels of Trakya University Keşan Hakkı Yörük School of Health students were investigated; It was determined that 65.83% (n:131) of the students did not think that they were individually prepared for an earthquake [7]. In the study conducted to evaluate the disaster preparedness and disaster awareness levels of Trakya University Keşan Vocational College students; It was found that 68.25% (n:86) of the students did not consider themselves prepared for disasters [9]. In the study conducted to determine the disaster awareness and disaster preparedness levels of Trakya University Keşan Hakkı Yörük School of Health students; It was determined that 71.03% (n:103) of the students did not consider themselves prepared for possible disasters [10]. In the study which the disaster awareness and disaster preparedness levels of Burdur Mehmet Akif Ersoy University Faculty of Economics and Administrative Sciences students were evaluated; It was reported that 78.3% (n:270) of the students did not consider themselves prepared for possible disasters [6]. The research findings support the findings in the literature.

In the study, it was determined that 76.98% (n:97) of the students did not have earthquake bags ready in their living spaces. In the study which the earthquake knowledge and earthquake awareness levels of Trakya University Keşan Hakkı Yörük School of Health students were investigated; It was determined that 83.42% (n:166) of the students did not have earthquake bags ready in their living spaces [7]. In the study conducted to determine the disaster awareness and disaster preparedness levels of Trakya University Keşan Vocational College students; It was determined that 74.60% (n:94) of the students did not prepare their disaster and emergency bags [9]. In the study conducted to determine the disaster awareness and disaster preparedness levels of Trakya University Keşan Hakkı Yörük School of Health students; It was observed that 77.93% (n:113) of the students did not prepare their disaster and emergency bags [10]. In the study which medical faculty students' knowledge, attitudes and behaviors about disasters and disaster medicine were evaluated; It was reported that 88.2% (n:755) of the students participating in the study did not keep a disaster kit in their living spaces [11]. In a study conducted to determine the earthquake awareness of students of the Vocational School of Health Services at a state university; It was reported that 72.4% (n:257) of the students did not have an earthquake emergency kit where they lived [5]. In the study which the disaster awareness and disaster preparedness levels of Burdur Mehmet Akif Ersoy University Faculty of Economics and Administrative Sciences students were evaluated; It was published that 86.7% (n:299) of the students did not have an earthquake kit [6]. In the study which the basic disaster awareness and preparedness levels of Gümüşhane University Kelkit Aydın Doğan Vocational School students were evaluated; It was reported that 88.7% (n:236) of the students did not have an emergency kit [8]. The research findings support the findings in the literature.

In the study, it was found that 69.05% (n:87) of the students had furniture that could tip over in their living spaces that was not fixed. In the study which the earthquake knowledge and earthquake awareness levels of Trakya University Keşan Hakkı Yörük School of Health students were investigated; It was determined that 88.44% (n:176) of the students had unsecured

furniture in their living spaces that could tip over [7]. In the study which the sustainable earthquake awareness levels of Düzce University students were examined in terms of different variables; It was reported that 61.55% (n:341) of the students did not fix their belongings that could fall to the walls in their homes or dormitories [4]. In the study which the disaster awareness and disaster preparedness levels of Burdur Mehmet Akif Ersoy University Faculty of Economics and Administrative Sciences students were evaluated; It was published that 60.9% (n:210) of the students did not fix the items in their homes to the wall or floor [6]. The research findings support the findings in the literature.

In the study, it was determined that 94.44% (n:119) of the students estimated that being aware of earthquakes could save lives. In the study which the earthquake knowledge and earthquake awareness levels of Trakya University Keşan Hakkı Yörük School of Health students were investigated; It was determined that 88.94% (n:177) of the students predicted that being aware of earthquakes could save lives [7]. In the study conducted to evaluate the disaster preparedness and disaster awareness levels of Trakya University Keşan Vocational College students; It was found that 92.06% (n:116) of the students had the idea that being aware of disasters could save lives [9]. In the study conducted to determine the disaster awareness and disaster preparedness levels of Trakya University Keşan Hakkı Yörük School of Health students; It was determined that 94.48% (n:137) of the students believed that being aware of disasters could save lives [10]. In a study conducted to determine the earthquake awareness of students of the Vocational School of Health Services at a state university; It was reported that 97.5% (n:346) of the students were aware that being aware of earthquakes could sometimes save lives [5]. The research findings support the findings in the literature.

In the study, it was determined that 57.94% (n:73) of the students were not aware of the existence of alternative shelters after the earthquake. In the study which the earthquake knowledge and earthquake awareness levels of Trakya University Keşan Hakkı Yörük School of Health students were investigated; It was determined that 71.36% (n:142) of the students did not know alternative shelters after the earthquake [7]. In the study conducted to evaluate the disaster preparedness and disaster awareness levels of Trakya University Keşan Vocational College students; It was observed that 64.29% (n:81) of the students did not know where their alternative accommodation was after the disaster [9]. In the study conducted to determine the disaster awareness and disaster preparedness levels of Trakya University Keşan Hakkı Yörük School of Health students; It was determined that 78.62% (n:114) of the students did not know where their alternative accommodation was after the disaster (10)[10]. In a study conducted to determine the earthquake awareness of students of the Vocational School of Health Services at a state university; It was reported that 72.4% (n:257) of the students did not have alternative shelter opportunities after the earthquake where they lived [5]. The research findings support the findings in the literature.

In the study, it was determined that 51.59% (n:65) of the students received earthquake-related training. In the study which the earthquake knowledge and earthquake awareness levels of Trakya University Keşan Hakkı Yörük School of Health students were investigated; It was found that 56.78% (n:113) of the students received earthquake-related training [7]. In the study investigating the knowledge and awareness levels of nursing students regarding disasters; It was reported that 60.8% of the students received training on disaster [12]. In the study conducted to evaluate the disaster preparedness and disaster awareness levels of Trakya University Keşan Vocational College students; It was determined that 56.35% (n:71) of the students received training on disasters (9)[9]. In the study conducted to determine the disaster awareness and disaster preparedness levels of Trakya University Keşan Hakkı Yörük School of Health students; It was determined that 68.28% (n:99) of the students received disaster-related training [10]. The research findings support the findings in the literature.

In the study, it was found that 56.35% (n:71) of the students thought that their university education did not inform them about the earthquake (before, during and after). In the study which the earthquake knowledge and earthquake awareness levels of Trakya University Keşan Hakkı Yörük School of Health students were investigated; It was found that 51.26% (n:102) of the students thought that their university education did not inform them about the earthquake (before, during and after) [7]. In a study conducted to determine the earthquake awareness of students of the Vocational School of Health Services at a state university; It was reported that 36.9% (n:131) of the students believed that university education did not raise their awareness of natural disasters [5]. In the study which the disaster awareness and disaster preparedness levels of Burdur Mehmet Akif Ersoy University Faculty of Economics and Administrative Sciences students were evaluated; It was published that 68.2% (n:378) of the students were of the opinion that trainings and meetings regarding earthquakes were not organized at the university they studied at, and also 66.79% (n:370) of the students were of the opinion that training and

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meetings regarding earthquakes were not organized at the university they studied at [6]. The research findings support the findings in the literature.

In the study, it was found that 75.40% (n:95) of the students had knowledge about the teams that should go to the scene after the earthquake. In the study which the earthquake knowledge and earthquake awareness levels of Trakya University Keşan Hakkı Yörük School of Health students were investigated; It was determined that 67.84% (n:135) of the students had an idea about which teams should go to the scene after the earthquake [7]. In the study conducted to evaluate the disaster preparedness and disaster awareness levels of Trakya University Keşan Vocational College students; It was determined that 71.43% (n:90) of the students knew which teams should go to the disaster area [9]. In the study conducted to determine the disaster awareness and disaster preparedness levels of Trakya University Keşan Hakkı Yörük School of Health students; It was determined that 65.52% (n:95) of the students were aware of the teams that should go to the disaster area [10]. The research findings support the findings in the literature.

In the study, it was seen that 65.08% (n:82) of the students did not have information about whether their schools/homes/dormitories were at risk of earthquake or not. In the study which the earthquake knowledge and earthquake awareness levels of Trakya University Keşan Hakkı Yörük School of Health students were investigated; It was determined that 60.80% (n:121) of the students were not aware of whether their schools and/or living spaces were at risk of earthquake [7]. In the study conducted to determine the disaster awareness and disaster preparedness levels of Trakya University Keşan Hakkı Yörük School of Health students; It was determined that 55.86% (n:81) of the students did not know the earthquake risk status of their schools/homes/dormitories [10]. In the study conducted to evaluate the disaster preparedness and disaster awareness levels of Trakya University Keşan Vocational College students; It was determined that 42.06% (n:53) of the students were not aware of whether their schools and/or the houses they lived in were at earthquake risk [9]. In a study conducted to determine the earthquake awareness of students of the Vocational School of Health Services at a state university; It was reported that 41.7% of the students did not know the physical earthquake risk status of the university where they studied [5]. The research findings support the findings in the literature.

In the study, it was determined that 62.70% (n:79) of the students knew the safe areas in their schools/homes/dormitories in case of a possible earthquake. In the study which the earthquake knowledge and earthquake awareness levels of Trakya University Keşan Hakkı Yörük School of Health students were investigated; It was determined that 51.03% (n:74) of the students knew the safe areas in their schools and/or living spaces in case of a disaster [7]. In the study conducted to evaluate the disaster preparedness and disaster awareness levels of Trakya University Keşan Vocational College students; It was determined that 62.70% (n:79) of the students knew the safe areas in their schools and/or living areas [9]. The research findings support the findings in the literature.

In the study, it was seen that 63.49% (n:80) of the students did not receive first aid training. In the study conducted to evaluate the disaster preparedness and disaster awareness levels of Trakya University Keşan Vocational College students; It was determined that 61.90% (n:78) of the students had first aid training [9]. In the study which the earthquake knowledge and earthquake awareness levels of Trakya University Keşan Hakkı Yörük School of Health students were investigated; It was determined that 44.72% (n:89) of the students did not receive first aid training [7]. In the study conducted to determine the disaster awareness and disaster preparedness levels of Trakya University Keşan Hakkı Yörük School of Health students; It was determined that 46.90% (n:68) of the students did not receive first aid training [10]. The research findings support the findings in the literature.

In the study, it was determined that 60.32% (n:76) of the students did not have earthquake-related applications on their phones. In the study which the earthquake knowledge and earthquake awareness levels of Trakya University Keşan Hakkı Yörük School of Health students were investigated; It was determined that 62.81% (n:125) of the students did not have earthquake-related applications on their phones [7].

In the study, it was determined that 78.57% (n:99) of the students had knowledge about how to evacuate their schools/homes/dormitories during an earthquake. In the study which the earthquake knowledge and earthquake awareness levels of Trakya University Keşan Hakkı Yörük School of Health students were investigated; It was determined that 60.30% (n:120) of the students had information about how to evacuate their schools and/or living spaces during an earthquake [7]. In the study conducted to evaluate the disaster preparedness and disaster awareness levels of Trakya University Keşan Vocational College students; It was found that 82.54% (n:104) of the students were aware of the need to evacuate their

schools and/or living spaces [9]. In the study conducted to determine the disaster awareness and disaster preparedness levels of Trakya University Keşan Hakkı Yörük School of Health students; It was determined that 72.41% (n:105) of the students had an idea about how to evacuate their school/home/dormitory [10]. In the study which the sustainable earthquake awareness levels of Düzce University students were examined in terms of different variables; It was reported that 59.2% (n:327) of the students knew how to evacuate their schools in case of a possible danger [4]. The research findings support the findings in the literature.

In the study, it was determined that 71.43% (n:90) of the students did not trust the earthquake resistance of their schools/homes/dormitories. In the study which the earthquake knowledge and earthquake awareness levels of Trakya University Keşan Hakkı Yörük School of Health students were investigated; It was determined that 85.93% (n:171) of the students did not trust the durability of their schools and/or living spaces against an earthquake [7].

It was determined that 58.73% (n:74) of the students participating in the study did not find the emergency exit directions in their schools/homes/dormitories sufficient. In the study which the earthquake knowledge and earthquake awareness levels of Trakya University Keşan Hakkı Yörük School of Health students were investigated; It was stated that 85.93% (n:171) of the students thought that the emergency exit directions in their schools and/or living spaces were not sufficient [7]. In the study which the sustainable earthquake awareness levels of Düzce University students were examined in terms of different variables; It was reported that 40.97% (n:227) of the students had the opinion that emergency exit directions were not sufficient in the faculty building of the university where they studied [4]. Research findings are similar to findings in the literature.

In the study, it was seen that 83.33% (n:105) of the students participated in the earthquake drill. In the study which the earthquake knowledge and earthquake awareness levels of Trakya University Keşan Hakkı Yörük School of Health students were investigated; It was determined that 80.40% (n:160) of the students participated in the earthquake drill [7]. In the study conducted to evaluate the disaster preparedness and disaster awareness levels of Trakya University Keşan Vocational College students; It was determined that 74.60% (n:94) of the students participated in a drill related to disasters [9]. In the study conducted to determine the disaster awareness and disaster preparedness levels of Trakya University Keşan Hakkı Yörük School of Health students; It was determined that 79.31% (n:115) of the students took part in a drill related to disasters [10]. The research findings support the findings in the literature.

The study found that 80.16% (n:101) of the students thought that local governments did not take the necessary precautions against a possible earthquake. In the study which the earthquake knowledge and earthquake awareness levels of Trakya University Keşan Hakkı Yörük School of Health students were investigated; It was determined that 90.95% (n:181) of the students did not think that local governments took the necessary precautions against an earthquake [7].

In the study, it was found that 91.27% (n:115) of the students had knowledge about earthquake gathering areas. In the study conducted to evaluate the disaster preparedness and disaster awareness levels of Trakya University Keşan Vocational College students; It was stated that 63.49% (n:80) of the students had an idea about where the meeting areas of their schools and/or living areas are located in case of a disaster [9].

Humankind has struggled with disasters throughout civilizations and continues to do so. Among natural disasters, earthquakes have caused the most damage and loss of life in human history [2, 3]. Within the framework of the philosophy of safe life and safe settlement, efforts have been made to reduce disaster damages. For this purpose, countries have come together, joined forces, established collaborations and carried out joint studies in the face of disasters that know no borders [13]. The basic principles of earthquake protection have been created with common sense in the world by conscious and modern societies that do not want to be harmed in an earthquake, and countries have adapted and implemented these basic principles according to their own positions and lifestyles [14].

Coping behaviors of individuals before, during and after an earthquake they may encounter; It is related to earthquake knowledge, consciousness, awareness and preparedness levels [12]. Studies have shown that society's awareness and education about earthquakes is insufficient [4, 5, 15, 16]. The society and individuals should receive training, be knowledgeable and conscious about earthquakes; It is important for them to be prepared for disasters and to take the necessary precautions. In order to raise awareness and educate the society, it is necessary to first determine the knowledge and awareness levels of the young population in the society about earthquakes [4, 15, 16].

It is necessary to create a culture of harm reduction in the society by carrying out comprehensive training activities covering all relevant segments of the society regarding disaster harm reduction. The consciousness of being a single individual is aimed at survival, and the consciousness of being a citizen is aimed at joint collective action. If the individual is made collective with citizen consciousness, the super-identity will begin to function on survival [13]. This study, in which the earthquake knowledge and earthquake awareness levels of students studying at five different programs of the vocational college are determined, and the studies to be carried out on this subject will support social mastery of disaster risk management.

V. CONCLUSION

According to data; Although the earthquake knowledge levels of vocational college students are high, it has been understood that their earthquake awareness levels need to be increased. The most important factor that plays a role in disaster management and society's earthquake preparedness is education [17, 18]. In order to ensure that the understanding of mitigation and preparedness reaches all segments of society as a part of earthquake culture, education and training activities on earthquakes need to be planned, developed and maintained [19].

Earthquake is an inevitable fact of nature and is a part of our lives. However, society's resistance to earthquakes can be increased with the right information and preparations. The first thing to do to create earthquake awareness in the society and prepare the society for an earthquake is; These include organizing campaigns informing the public, providing regular training in schools and workplaces, and providing access to accurate and reliable information about earthquake risk and protection methods. Additionally, community-based emergency plans bring together individuals in neighborhoods, apartments, or workplaces to raise awareness about how to act in the event of an earthquake. Earthquake drills and simulations held at regular intervals also teach individuals the right behaviors to be applied during an earthquake. Creating earthquake awareness and preparing the society against earthquakes is the key to a safe future. A society that is conscious and prepared for earthquakes will be more resilient in dealing with earthquakes.

The resilient individual and society model should be at the center of disaster management policy. Resilience for societies is defined as the ability of the society to meet the earthquake with a capacity built on psychological competence and the common identity to be created for this purpose. The common identity shared as a society is understanding the disaster and creating a social identity based on it. By reproducing the common identity in the event of an earthquake, it should be aimed to achieve effective psychological intervention and preventive practices. It should be believed that the creation of a shared common identity during the earthquake preparation phase will increase individual and social resilience capacity and efforts to cope with the effects of the earthquake to a very high level [20].

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